

TEACHING THE APPLICATION OF SPELLING RULES FOR UNSTRESSED VOWELS

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Abstract. The article examines methodological approaches to teaching the spelling rules of unstressed vowels in national-language groups. Special attention is paid to the scheme of oral and written orthographic analysis, which enables students to consciously master spelling rules and apply them in practice.

Keywords: unstressed vowels, orthographic analysis, verifiable unstressed vowel, test word, explanation of spelling patterns, identifying feature of a spelling pattern.

Introduction. Teaching orthography in national-language groups requires a systematic approach based on the step-by-step analysis of spelling patterns. When explaining a rule, the teacher should provide a clear description of the orthographic analysis scheme and demonstrate models of both oral and written explanations.

Methodology of Orthographic Analysis

1. Unstressed Root Vowels Verified by Stress

Identification stage: detecting an unstressed vowel.

Classification stage: determining its position in the word (root, prefix, etc.).

Final stage: selecting a test word in which the vowel is stressed.

Examples:

вода → воды (water → waters)

ночь → ночной (night → nightly)

2. Unstressed Vowels in Prefixes

Vowels in prefixes are written in the same way as under stress:

описать → опись

записать → запись

Analysis scheme:

Identify the unstressed vowel.

Determine the morpheme in which it occurs.

If the prefix is pre- or pri-, determine the correct vowel (e or i) according to the rule.

Examples:

предписать → e

надписать → a

подписать → o

3. Alternating Vowels in the Root

Special attention is paid to vowel alternations in roots:

лож-/лаг- → лож (o), лаг (a)

рос-/раст-/ращ- → the choice of vowel depends on the following consonant:

вырос

вырасти

выращенный

Example of an oral explanation:

In the word *predlagat'* (предлагать), the unstressed vowel occurs in the root -lag-.

According to the rule governing the alternation лаг-/лож-, the letter a is written in the root -lag-. In the word *predlozhit'* (предложить), the root is -lozh-, where the letter o is written. *o*.

Type of Vowel	Identifying Feature	Verification Method	Examples	Sample Explanation
Verifiable	Unstressed vowel in the root	Selection of a test word with stress on the vowel	<i>voda</i> – <i>vody</i> (water – waters), <i>noch'</i> –	In the word <i>voda</i> , there is an unstressed vowel in the root.

Type of Vowel	Identifying Feature	Verification Method	Examples	Sample Explanation
			<i>nochnoy</i> (night – nightly)	The test word is <i>vody</i> , where the vowel is stressed.
Non-verifiable	Unstressed vowel in the root	Memorization; dictionary reference	<i>moloko</i> (milk), <i>sobaka</i> (dog), <i>vorobey</i> (sparrow)	In the word <i>moloko</i> , there is an unstressed vowel in the root. There is no test word; therefore, the spelling must be memorized.
Alternating	Unstressed vowel in the root with alternation (<i>a–o, e–i</i>)	Identification of the root and the conditions governing vowel alternation	<i>predlagat'</i> – propose – to offer), <i>vyrasty</i> – grow – grew)	In the word <i>predlagat'</i> , the root - <i>lag-</i> contains the letter a . In the word <i>predlozhit'</i> , the root - <i>lozh-</i> contains the letter o .
Prefix Vowel	Unstressed vowel in a prefix	Identification of the type of prefix (<i>pri-</i> / <i>pre-</i> or others)	<i>predpisat'</i> , <i>nadpisat'</i> , <i>podpisat'</i>	In the word <i>predpisat'</i> , the prefix <i>pred-</i> is always written with the letter e .

Practical Significance

The application of the orthographic analysis scheme:

develops students' skills of conscious word analysis;
promotes the development of spelling awareness and orthographic vigilance;
ensures the durable acquisition of spelling rules and their effective application in written communication.

Orthographic Analysis Scheme

Is there an unstressed vowel in the word?

- **No** → No rule application is required.
- **Yes** → Determine its position in the word.

1. In the Root

Determine whether the unstressed vowel is:

- **Verifiable** → Select a test word with the vowel under stress.
- **Non-verifiable** → Consult a dictionary or memorize the spelling.
- **Alternating** → Apply the corresponding vowel alternation rule.

Result: Write the word and provide an explanation of the spelling.

2. In the Prefix

Determine the type of prefix:

- **pre- / pri-** → Apply the relevant spelling rule.
- **Other prefixes (o, a, e)** → Follow the standard spelling pattern.

Result: Write the word and provide an explanation of the spelling.

Final Stage

Writing the word with an orthographic explanation.

- This scheme:
- begins with the identification stage, which involves detecting an unstressed vowel;
- then divides the analysis according to the location of the vowel in either the root or the prefix;
- demonstrates how to determine the type of vowel (verifiable, non-verifiable, or alternating) or the type of prefix;

- concludes with a written explanation of the word's spelling.
- Thus, students acquire a universal algorithm that can be applied to any word containing an unstressed vowel.
- Перевод таблицы на английский язык для научной статьи:

Root Pattern	Exceptions	Explanation
-rast- / -ros-	<i>rostok</i> (sprout), <i>Rostov</i> , <i>otrasl'</i> (industry/branch), <i>rostovshchik</i> (moneylender)	In these words, the letter o is written despite the consonants that normally determine the vowel choice in the root. These spellings are exceptions and must be memorized.
-skak- / -skoch-	<i>skachok</i> (jump), <i>skakun</i> (racehorse/jumper)	The regular a–o alternation rule does not apply in these words. Their spelling is exceptional and should be memorized.

Conclusion

Systematic work on spelling rules and the use of oral and written orthographic analysis schemes enable students not only to apply spelling rules correctly but also to develop a conscious understanding of orthographic phenomena in the Russian language. Such an approach enhances spelling awareness, strengthens orthographic competence, and contributes to the formation of stable literacy skills.

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